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DIAGNOSTICALLY ROBUST ULTRASOUND VIDEO TRANSMISSION OVER EMERGING WIRELESS NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this project is to develop a unifying framework for the error-resilient communication of medical ultrasound video over emerging 3.5G and 4G wireless networks that is suitable for critically-needed clinical diagnosis. The goal is to develop new methods as well as integrate state-of-the-art methods in video coding, wireless networks, and medical video quality assessment into an adaptive, automated framework. The anticipated system will be validated in cardiovascular remote diagnosis applications. In this study, we summarize conducted research achievements, discuss ongoing work and preliminary findings, and highlight future work in each of the afore-described disciplines parting mobile-health (m-health) video systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical video communication m-health systems can provide significant time advantages, especially within the first, “golden hour”, of an emergency incident, that can prove decisive for the patients’ status assessment, on-site care, and long-term recovery. In addition to emergency telematics at the incident scene and within ambulance care, such systems can be deployed at disaster episodes for enhancing emergency management decision, and better triage support. Moreover, to accommodate remote diagnosis and care for the elderly and people with mobility problems, for mass population screening purposes, which is of vital importance in developing countries, as well as for medical education purposes and second opinion provision (see Fig. 1).

Despite the rapid growth of m-health medical video communication systems over the past decade [1]-[3], there has been limited adoption of such systems and services. The objective of this project is to develop a unifying framework for the error-resilient communication of medical ultrasound video over emerging 3.5G and 4G wireless networks that can approach the experience of in-hospital care. The goal is to develop new methods as well as integrate state-of-the-art methods in video coding, wireless networks, and medical video quality assessment into an adaptive, automated system. It is anticipated that the successful completion of this project will aid in the adoption of medical video communication systems in daily clinical practice. Here, we summarize conducted research achievements, discuss on-going work and preliminary findings, and highlight future work in each of the afore-described disciplines. For each case we provide references to the in-depth implementation analyses of the abstracted work depicted here.

II. MEDICAL VIDEO CODING

Optimal video encoding parameters selection is of essential importance in the design of medical video communication systems. The proper trade-off between compression and clinical performance should be investigated so as not to compromise the medical video’s diagnostic capacity. Moreover, different data transfer speeds supported by different wireless networks impose quality constraints on the compressed bitstream. Therefore, in real-time adaptive m-health video streaming systems, threshold video encoding parameters values should be determined a priori, in order to ensure that the employed parameter configuration will not fall below of what is clinically acceptable. Moreover, specific encoding parameters such as video resolution and frame rates directly impact the diagnostic capacity of the communicated ultrasound video, in addition to the incurred bitrate demands. The latter also caters for different end-user equipment including a plethora of mobile devices. For atherosclerotic plaque ultrasound video, clinical evaluation criteria range according to the employed video size, while clinical

Fig. 1. M-health medical video communication systems application scenarios. Using the best available wireless network, medical video is transmitted from the incident side to the medical expert's side for remote diagnosis .

TABLE I
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CLINICAL CRITERIA AND VIDEO RESOLUTION¹

	QCIF	CIF	4CIF
<i>Plaque Detection</i>	√	√	√
<i>Artery Stenosis</i>	√	√	√
<i>Plaque Type</i>		√	√
<i>Plaque Morphology</i>			√

¹Table based on [4].

motion is highly affected by video's frame rate. Table I summarizes the findings of investigated video resolution association to atherosclerotic plaque clinical criteria, depicted in [4]. The proposed medical video transmission system diagram in this study appears in Fig. 2 [5]. The depicted diagram includes two operation modes. The first mode is used to determine diagnostically acceptable encoding configurations prior to the wireless communication, and therefore the blocks contained in the rectangle annotated by the dotted line which deal with wireless transmission, video decoding, and real-time system adaptation are not considered. An iterative procedure is used where encoding parameters including video resolution, frame rates, and quantization factors are varied for an adequate sample of medical videos. For each case, the medical expert evaluates their diagnostic capacity and provides a clinical score. A look up table is then created where diagnostically acceptable encoding parameters combinations are stored, to be retrieved during real-time system operation. In the second mode of operation including all blocks, a coarse to fine parameter optimization is used to derive the optimum encoding and network parameter setup that maximizes the diagnostic capacity of the communicated video, for different scenarios that simulate the

Fig. 2 System diagram of the proposed end-to-end medical video transmission system (based on [5]).

varying conditions characterizing wireless video transmission. The trade-off between error resiliency and encoding efficiency for reliable performance in noisy environments is also investigated. The aim is to maximize medical video's diagnostic robustness by adapting to the constantly varying wireless network state while conforming to the established diagnostically lossless threshold values and balancing encoding efficiency. For a detail description of the proposed medical video communication framework the reader is referred to [5]-[5].

Diagnostically Relevant Encoding

The key concept here, which is also applicable to other medical video modalities (see [3]-[7]), is that certain video regions contain the clinical information that is needed to assess certain clinical criteria. Classification of these video regions according to the assessed clinical criteria allows the specification of video slices for independent encoding. The video quality of each slice is then controlled by setting the value of the corresponding QP, with respect to its clinical significance. As a result, diagnostically relevant encoding is achieved, providing for efficient utilization of the network's resources. The proposed diagnostically relevant encoding is implemented using H.264/AVC flexible macroblock ordering (FMO) error resilience technique. FMO type 2 allows the specification of rectangular regions-of-interest (ROIs), which are then assigned to different slices for

Fig. 3. Diagnostically relevant encoding of atherosclerotic plaque ultrasound video [4]-[6]. (a) Pixel-based segmentation of diagnostically important regions, (b) Quantization Parameter Allocation Map (QPAmmap) for diagnostically relevant encoding, (c) The corresponding FMO type 2 Macroblock Allocation Map (MBAmmap).

independent encoding. Fig. 3 depicts diagnostically relevant encoding (or variable quality slice encoding) for atherosclerotic plaque ultrasound videos. The diagnostic ROIs are the plaque region, the area between near and far artery walls, as well as the ECG at the bottom right of the video. The remaining regions are of limited clinical interest. Adopting variable quality slice encoding can lead to significant bitrate demands reductions without compromising clinical capacity. Indicatively, for scalable QCIF, CIF, and 4CIF resolutions, bitrate demands savings of 34.7%, 39.8%, and 42.3% are achieved, respectively (see Table II [4]).

High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) vs H.264/AVC

The Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC), established by the ITU-T VCEG and the ISO/IEC MPEG groups issued a joint call for proposals (CfP) in 2010 to initiate the process of the new video coding standard, termed high efficiency video coding (HEVC). The emerging HEVC standard is expected in January 2013. While it maintains the block-based structure found in all previous standards, new coding tools, enhanced intra and inter prediction mechanisms via enriched motion compensation and motion vector prediction modes, in addition to refinement of established tools, provide significant bitrate demands reductions for equivalent perceptual quality. More specifically, bitrate demands gains of 40.3% have been recorded for interactive applications compared to the H.264/AVC standard, while 35.4% bitrate savings are achieved for entertainment applications. The goal here is to exploit the benefits of using the new HEVC standard for ultrasound video communications, and integrate it in the proposed medical video transmission framework.

The HM test model is the HEVC reference software, used to evaluate the new design elements of HEVC standard. For that reason, it defines common test conditions, also for H.264/AVC comparison. For different application requirements it defines random-access and low-delay modes, while for different encoding tools, HM used to define high-efficiency (including all coding tools, somewhat computationally intensive) and main (including mainstream features) schemes. However, in the new standard, HEVC is likely to define a single profile termed Main, and therefore in later releases, high-efficiency and main modes have

TABLE II
AVERAGE BIT RATE GAINS OF DIAGNOSTICALLY
RELEVANT ENCODING FOR THE SAME DIAGNOSTIC
QUALITY FOR FMO ROI RS vs FMO¹

	QCIF	CIF	4CIF
Bit Rate Gain (%)	34.7	39.8	42.3

¹FMO ROI RS stands for variable quality slice encoding with redundant slices. FMO stands for standard H.264/AVC FMO type 2 encoding [4].

TABLE III
AVERAGE BITRATE GAINS OF EMERGING HEVC
STANDARD WHEN COMPARED TO H.264/AVC
STANDARD FOR RANDOM ACCESS AND LOW DELAY
MODES FOR THE SAME DIAGNOSTIC QUALITY

HEVC vs H.264/AVC	¹ RA_HE	² LB_HE
	vs JM_RA_B_HE	vs JM_LP_HE
Bit Rate Gain (%)	36.5%	37.3%

¹HEVC random-access high-efficiency mode vs H.264/AVC random-access high-efficiency mode.

²HEVC low-delay high-efficiency (using B-pictures) scheme vs H.264/AVC low-delay high-efficiency (using P-pictures) scheme [10].

converged. Finally, HM allows for all intra pictures, P-pictures, and B-pictures (default). Similarly, JM H.264/AVC reference software defines two common test conditions, namely random-access high efficiency using B-Pictures and low-delay high efficiency using P-pictures. The results of HEVC vs H.264/AVC coding efficiency gains for ultrasound video communications are summarized in Table III. Random-access mode achieves bitrate demands reductions of 36.5%, while low-delay scheme provides for 37.3% bitrate gains. For both configurations, clinical evaluation verifies that diagnostic capacity of HEVC encoded videos are at least of the same quality as the H.264/AVC encoded video. A detail experimental setup, results analyses, and discussion appear in [8]-[10].

III. WIRELESS NETWORKS

Wireless networks are a rapid growing area, especially in the last decade. Data transfer rates have climbed to tens of megabits per second (Mbps) with the new 3.5G wireless channels, while 4G channels target download rates of 1Gbps. Such rates could be only found in wired infrastructure some years ago. M-health systems have exploited advances in wireless networks to provide for more reliable systems, with wider coverage, toward an always-on communication model, also aided by the emergence of high performance portable devices. Despite these advancements, medical video transmission at the acquired resolution and frame rates was not feasible with 3G (and beyond) wireless channels, as the upload data rates of these channels imposed constraints on the afore-described parameters. As documented in [3]-[4] most m-health video communications systems were limited to CIF (352x288) resolution and usually up to 15 fps medical video transmission. Given the association of clinical criteria and video resolution depicted in Table I, new 3.5G and emerging 4G wireless networks are expected to provide for high-resolution, high frame rate, and low-delay medical video communications that will accommodate the diagnostic ultrasound video capacity of in-hospital examination.

The latter is expected to aid in adopting m-health video communication systems in daily clinical practice.

For the purposes of this project, we aim at exploiting the benefits associated by incorporating new 3.5G and 4G wireless channels in m-health video communications systems. To accomplish that, we evaluate efficient network parameters' setting that maximizes ultrasound's video diagnostic capacity for different wireless channels, both via simulations and real-time setups. Next, we present a case study for real-time ultrasound video communications over 3.5G HSPA channels to appear in [11]. Mobile WiMAX networks capacity to deliver high diagnostic quality video has been extensively investigated in [4].

High Speed Packet Access (HSPA) Networks

We investigate currently available 3.5G mobile cellular networks performance in Cyprus using an open-source telemedicine platform developed for this purpose. The platform is composed of top performing open-source tools, and the objective is to bridge the gap between theory and practice while delivering adequate quality diagnostic quality medical video using low-cost solutions. Source encoding is performed using the x264 codec, wireless transmission via the VLC player, QoS measurements are derived using the Wireshark network monitor, while objective video quality assessment (VQA) is based on PSNR ratings following variable frame delay (VFD) calibration. Finally, the communicated videos are clinically evaluated by a medical expert. Such a system is of critical importance for providing mass population screening and remote diagnosis, especially in developing countries.

Five atherosclerotic plaque ultrasound videos, with spatial video resolution of 560x416 acquired at 40 frames per second (fps) were used to evaluate commercially available HSPA cellular networks in Cyprus. Scalable video resolutions, namely QCIF, CIF, and 560x416 that reflect the most common resolutions used in atherosclerotic plaque ultrasound video transmission (also 4CIF), bitrates (QCIF: 64 kbps – 324 kbps, CIF: 128 kbps -512 kbps, 560x416: 512 kbps – 768 kbps), as well as different encoding schemes (IPPP, IPBBP, IPBBBBP, and IPBBBBBBBP) and profiles for investigating coding efficiency summarize the experimental evaluation setup. Results were averaged over 5 transmissions for each case, at different time periods, for realistic performance.

Fig. 4 presents the results of the higher resolution ultrasound video transmission using the IPBBBBBP coding structure for ultrasound videos encoded at bitrates of 512 kbps and 768 kbps. PSNR ratings are depicted using boxplots for the compressed ultrasound video prior to transmission (leftmost boxplots), after transmission (middle boxplots), and after transmission following VFD calibration (rightmost boxplots). A very important observation is that PSNR ratings are extremely low prior to applying VFD calibration, and fall significantly below than

Fig. 4. PSNR vs Bitrate boxpots for the investigated ultrasound video data set (560x415@15fps, IPBBBBP coding structure) [11].

TABLE IV. CLINICAL EVALUATION OF VIDEOS TRANSMITTED USING COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE HSPA NETWORKS

Bitrate (kbps)	512	768
Plaque Detection	5	5
Artery Stenosis	5	5
Plaque Type	4	4

1: Lowest score , 5: Highest score
560x415@15fps, IPBBBBP coding structure

the diagnostically acceptable PSNR threshold of 35 dB documented in [5]-[6]. The reasoning comes from temporal pauses present in the received video, which causes PSNR algorithm to fail to correlate with perceived video quality. The latter happens because PSNR VQA algorithm compares consecutive video frames of the received and original video. As a result, a temporal mismatch will cause misaligned frames to be compared, and therefore the incurred PSNR ratings will not be objective. Given the high probability of wireless networks to introduce such a delay, the VFD algorithm was specifically developed to remove temporal mismatch between transmitted and received videos. Employing VFD algorithm as a calibration step before computing VQA metrics, results in more accurate performance measurements, closer to perceived video quality. This is the case in Fig. 4, where PSNR ratings of received videos are comparable to the original videos prior to transmission. The latter observation is also verified using by the clinical evaluation, where clinically acceptable scores were assigned to the received videos. Table V summarizes clinical ratings for a single video, but the trend is the same for all investigated videos. The rating scale is from one to five, with five being the highest score, and one being the lowest. A rating of four signifies the loss of some clinical information (plaque motion details in this case), but the video still qualifies for clinical practice. Individual ratings are provided for the following clinical criteria: a) Plaque Detection, b) Artery Stenosis, and c) Plaque type. A thorough analysis of this work appears in [11].

IV. CLINICAL VIDEO QUALITY ASSESSMENT

There are unique challenges associated with both objective and subjective clinical VQA. In addition to the motion and QoS aspects of conventional VQA, unique clinical criteria, often different for each medical modality, need to be properly assessed. These clinical criteria often correspond to specific video portions that are of diagnostic interest. These regions of diagnostic interest are much more sensitive to compression and error impairments given their significant clinical contribution to the diagnostic yield of the particular medical video. On the other hand,

diagnostic ROI encoding may lead to diagnostically lossless medical videos. Clearly, both schemes are not adequately assessed by current objective VQA algorithms. Hence, there is a clear demand for developing diagnostically-driven VQA metrics, based on a weighted sum of objective measurements computed over video regions of different clinical importance.

For subjective clinical evaluation, while we do expect that the basic features of subjective quality assessment criteria of general purpose video will play a role in emerging medical video quality assessment standards, unique clinical criteria will also need to be adequately modeled. Diagnostic yield of transmitted medical video is restricted by a number of factors including resolution, frame rate, and end user equipment. Diagnostic capacity of a QCIF resolution medical video at 15 fps displayed on a PDA largely differs from a 4CIF resolution at 30 fps displayed on a laptop. Hence, appropriate clinical rating schemes should also address the aforementioned implications.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper describes current advances and future directions in the design of m-health medical video communication systems documented via the Diagnostically Robust Ultrasound Video Transmission Over Emerging Wireless Networks “DRIVEN” project. A diagnostically relevant encoding approach has been proposed where video regions are assigned quality levels proportional to their diagnostic capacity. This scheme provides for significant bitrate demands reductions (42.3% for 4CIF video resolution) without compromising diagnostic quality. Toward this end, the emerging HEVC standard achieves bitrate gains of 36.5% and 37.3%, for random access and low delay modes, respectively, when compared to the H.264/AVC standard. In terms of wireless infrastructure, both mobile WIMAX and HSPA 3.5G wireless networks have shown to support low-delay and high-resolution medical video transmission, close to the standards of in-hospital examinations.

On-going includes investigating error-resilient encoding setups using HEVC over 4G wireless networks. Future work is directed towards developing diagnostically-driven VQA algorithm for efficient assessment of the clinical capacity of the communicated ultrasound video that will correlate with medical experts ratings.

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